

Effect of e-Supply Chain Management on the Business Process of Airline Industry

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to cover topic of e-Supply chain management (SCM) from the passengers prospective. E-supply chain makes the process easy and it helped to save time. This research focuses on the major airlines of the Pakistan and will try to cover, weather passengers are enjoying the e-supply chain or self-service technologies or not? Are the passengers satisfied with this e-supply chain or not? Primary data have been collected with the help of survey and questionnaire from the customers of different airlines of Pakistan on domestic and international flights.

Key words: e-Supply Chain Management, Airline, Survey Analysis

E-SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

The impression that the internet have on the business process from the raw material to the end user including manufacturers, suppliers and distributors. ESCM add value to the business and it gives more satisfaction to the customers and stakeholders. Internet has three main impacts on the supply chain. First is *e-commerce* which shows how organizations or companies meet with the challenges with the internet when the goods or services are sold through the internet. Another aspect is *information sharing*. How the companies respond when the internet help to share the information between the company and stakeholder. *Information sharing* is also helpful in the service industry .It helped the customer to know about the current information of the services, for example in the airline industry internet is helpful it gives the information about the flight status and reservation and services of the airline. *Knowledge sharing* is the third aspect which is used in the ESCM it helps in the planning and the decision making.

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND SELF-SERVICE TECHNOLOGY

In recent time self-service Technology (SSTs) is the most attractive way to improve the customer satisfaction [1]. Self-service technologies are related to the e-supply chain and internet. SST gives full authority to the customer to enjoy the

services of company without involving any staff of the company [2]. SSTs improve productivity and it cut the cost and customer satisfaction [3]. In service provider industry SSTs increase accuracy and speed, it gives more organize services, save time, increase productivity and competition, gives more customer satisfaction [4]. Customer satisfaction and the service quality are the key factors to obtain the competitive advantage and the customer attention. The outcome of customer perception and value received from the service quality is the customer satisfaction [5-7].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Questionnaire methodology has been adopted for this research paper. The survey includes both domestic and international flights to maintain the broader view for the readers. This survey is conducted at the different airports of the Pakistan like Quaid-e-Azam International Airport Karachi, Allama Iqbal international airport Lahore, and Benazir international airport Islamabad. Three major international airlines customers included in the research that is Pakistan international Airline, Shaheen international Airlines, and Air blue. According to survey

Survey Questions	Yes	No
Age	20-35	
Do you purchase your ticket through website?	35%	15%
Do you allocate your seat u self?	44%	6%
You use self-service technology for boarding card?	20%	30%
Do you enjoy self-service technology?	45%	5%

Table 1 Questionnaire of Survey of Passengers having age 20 to 35 years

Table 2 Survey Analysis of Passengers having age 20 to 35 years

Survey has been conducted from the 50 passengers between age group of 20-35 and different questions have been asked from them. 35% passengers said that that they purchased their ticket themselves while 15% said that they do not. 44% passengers like to allocate their seat bur 6% do not. Same is the same when they have been asked that they like using the self-service boarding card technology while traveling then 20% said that they like but majority said that they do not like self-service boarding card technology. 45% are in favor of self-service technology and only 5% said they they do not like self-service technology. We can say that over all the young people like the self-service technology or we can say the e supply chain during traveling [8,9].

Survey Questions	Yes	No
Age	35-50	
Do you purchase your ticket through website?	20%	30%
Do you allocate your seat u self?	33%	17%
You use self-service technology for boarding card?	14%	36%
Do you enjoy self-service technology?	12%	38%

Table 3 Questionnaire of Survey of Passengers having age 35 to 50 years

Same survey has been conducted from the different age group of passengers. This time the age group was between the 35-50 years and results were also different from the previous survey. 20% passengers said that they like to purchase tickets themselves while 30% do not like to purchase themselves [10]. 17% do not like to allocate their seats while 33% like to allocate their seats. 36% do not like to use self-service technology to generate their boarding pass. Only 14% like to use this technology. 38% do not use

self-service technology.

Table 4 Survey Analysis of Passengers having age 35 to 50 years

CONCLUSION

To conclude this paper we can say that e-supply chain is becoming famous with the passage of time and young people of Pakistan are using the internet facilities for the airline traveling and other purposes. People who are above 35 years old are reluctant to use the internet because they are not habitual to use the internet or e supply chain in the daily life. According to survey efficient e supply chain effects on the business process in positive manner.

REFERENCES

1. V. Shankar, A. K. Smith, and A. Rangaswamy, "Customer satisfaction and loyalty in online and offline environments," *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 153-175, 2003
2. V. Liljander, F. Gillberg, J. Gummerus, and A. Van Riel, "Technology readiness and the evaluation and adoption of self-service technologies," *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 177-191, 2006.
3. P. A. Dabholkar, "Consumer evaluations of new technology-based selfservice options: an

investigation of alternative models of service quality," *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, vol. 13. no. 1, pp. 29-51, 1996.

4. G. Feuerlicht, "Design of service interfaces for e-business applications using data normalization techniques," *Information Systems and EBusiness Management*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 363-376, 2005.
5. D. M. Szymanski, and D. H. Henard, "Customer Satisfaction: A Meta- Analysis of the Empirical Evidence," *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 16-35, 2001.
6. Manivannan, M.S., 1998. Simulation of logistics and transportation systems. In: Banks, J. (Ed.), *Handbook of Simulation*. Wiley, New York, pp. 571-604.
7. Banks, J., Buckley, S., Jain, S., Lendermann, P., Manivannan, M., 2002. Panel session: Opportunities for simulation in supply chain management. *Proceedings from the 2002 Winter Simulation Conference*, 1652-1658
8. Banks, J. & Carsen, J. S., (1984) *Discret Event System Simulation*, Prentice-Hall.
9. Pegden, C. D., Shanon, R. E., & Sadowsky, R. (1990) *Introduction to Simulation Using SIMAN*, McGraw-Hill
10. Hollocks, B. (1992) A well-kept secret: Simulation manufacturing industry review. *OR Insight*. Vol.5, No.4, pp.12-17.